

Isolation and Screening of Potent L-Glutaminase Enzyme Producing Bacteria from Soil of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract:

L-Glutaminase (EC 3.5.1.2) is an amidohydrolase enzyme of considerable therapeutic, industrial and ecological significance that catalyzes the hydrolytic deamidation of L-glutamine to L-glutamic acid and ammonia. The present study was conducted to isolate, screen, characterize and produce crude L-glutaminase enzyme from soil bacteria collected from garden and forest sites of Government Institute of Science, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra, India. Serial dilution and spread plate technique on M9 minimal salt medium containing L-glutamine as the sole nitrogen source yielded six distinct bacterial isolates designated L1 to L6. Primary screening using phenol red indicator confirmed L-glutaminase activity in all six isolates through the development of pink or red halo zones. Morphological characterization by gram staining revealed that L2, L3 and L6 were gram positive while L1, L4 and L5 were gram negative. Negative staining confirmed diverse cell morphologies including cocci and rod-shaped cells. Biochemical characterization through IMViC, catalase and urease tests provided a comprehensive metabolic profile of each isolate. Secondary screening by Nessler's quantitative assay identified isolate L6 as the most potent L-glutaminase producer with the highest ammonia concentration of 0.58 mg/L per 5ml (OD 0.3870 at 456nm), followed by L3 (0.55 mg/L) and L2 (0.50 mg/L). Crude enzyme extract was successfully prepared by centrifugation of fermented broth at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. These results establish that local soil environments of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar harbour potent L-glutaminase producing bacteria with significant biotechnological and agricultural potential.

Keywords: *L-Glutaminase, Amidohydrolase, Soil bacteria, M9 medium, Phenol red, Nessler's test, Nitrogen metabolism, Biofertilizer.*

Introduction:

Enzymes are biological catalysts that play indispensable roles in metabolic processes and industrial applications. Among the diverse classes of enzymes, amidohydrolases have attracted considerable scientific and commercial interest due to their ability to catalyze the hydrolysis of amide bonds in biologically significant substrates. L-Glutaminase (L-glutamine amidohydrolase, EC 3.5.1.2) is one such enzyme that catalyzes the irreversible hydrolysis of L-glutamine to L-glutamic acid and ammonia, a reaction of

paramount importance in both cellular metabolism and various industrial processes (Unissa et al., 2014).

L-Glutamine is recognized as a conditionally essential amino acid serving as a primary nitrogen donor in biosynthetic reactions, including nucleotide and amino sugar synthesis. Furthermore, it plays a pivotal role as an energy source for rapidly proliferating cancer cells. L-Glutaminase, by depleting L-glutamine, exhibits antitumor and anti-leukemic properties, making it a subject of intensive biomedical research,

particularly for treatment of Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (Orabi et al., 2019). In addition to its therapeutic significance, L-Glutaminase finds extensive application in the food industry, where it enhances the umami flavor of fermented food products by converting glutamine to the flavor-imparting glutamate (Martinez et al., 2022).

Microorganisms represent the most exploited source of L-Glutaminase owing to their rapid growth kinetics, genetic tractability and high enzyme yields. Bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes are the major microbial groups reported to produce this enzyme. Among bacteria, species belonging to the genera *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Serratia* and *Streptomyces* have been widely studied for their L-Glutaminase producing capability (Desai et al., 2016; Sinha and Nigam, 2016; Kaushal et al., 2023). Soil is an exceptionally diverse ecological niche harbouring billions of microorganisms per gram, representing an enormous reservoir of novel enzyme-producing strains (Yadav et al., 2020).

Ecologically, L-Glutaminase plays a vital role in soil nitrogen cycling by catalyzing the hydrolysis of organic nitrogen compounds and releasing ammonium, which is subsequently

available for plant uptake, thereby contributing to soil fertility and supporting sustainable agriculture (Kim and Kwak, 2023). Despite the considerable body of research available, there remains a continuous demand for isolation of novel bacterial strains with enhanced enzyme production capabilities from regionally diverse soil ecosystems. The present study was therefore undertaken to isolate, screen, morphologically and biochemically characterize, and produce crude L-glutaminase from soil bacteria collected from Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra, India.

Materials and Methods:

1. Collection of Soil Samples:

Soil samples were collected from two distinct ecological sites namely a garden site and a forest site located within the campus of Government Institute of Science, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra, India (431001). Samples were collected from approximately 5 to 10 cm depth, stored in sterile polythene bags and transported to the laboratory for immediate processing.

Fig. 1. Soil sample collection from (a) forest site and (b) garden site, Government Institute of Science, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar.

2. Isolation on Selective Medium:

M9 minimal salt medium was used as the selective medium for isolation of L-glutaminase producing bacteria. The medium was composed of L-glutamine as the sole nitrogen source along with potassium chloride, sodium chloride, magnesium sulphate, potassium sulphate, ferrous sulphate, zinc sulphate and agar-agar. The pH was adjusted to 7.0 using 0.1N NaOH or 0.1N HCl.

The medium was sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes at 15 lbs pressure. Soil samples were serially diluted up to 10^{-6} and spread plated onto the selective medium under aseptic conditions. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 to 48 hours and only colonies showing visible growth were considered as potential L-glutaminase producers.

Fig. 2. Bacterial colonies grown on M9 minimal salt selective medium containing L-glutamine as sole nitrogen source.

3. Primary Screening Using Phenol Red Indicator:

Primary screening was performed using phenol red as a pH-sensitive colorimetric indicator incorporated into the M9 medium. L-Glutaminase positive colonies were identified by

the development of a distinct pink or magenta red halo zone around the colonies due to ammonia release causing an alkaline pH shift. The diameter of the color change zone around each colony was measured and compared to assess relative enzyme production potential among isolates.

Fig. 3. Primary screening using phenol red indicator showing pink/red halo zones around L-glutaminase positive colonies.

4. Morphological Characterization:

All six selected isolates were subjected to gram staining using crystal violet as primary stain, Gram's iodine as mordant, acetone-alcohol as decolorizer and safranin as counter stain.

Slides were observed under oil immersion lens at 100x magnification. Negative staining was performed using nigrosin dye to study the true cell morphology, size and arrangement without heat fixation distortion.

Fig. 4. Gram staining of isolates L1, L2, L3, L4, L5 and L6 observed under oil immersion lens (100x).

Fig. 5. Negative staining of isolates L1, L2, L3, L4, L5 and L6 showing cell morphology.

5. Biochemical Characterization:

All isolates were subjected to the IMViC test series comprising indole test using Kovac's reagent, methyl red test for mixed acid fermentation, Voges-Proskauer test using Barritt's reagent for acetoin production, and citrate utilization test on Simmons citrate agar. Catalase

test was performed by adding 3% hydrogen peroxide to bacterial colonies and observing for effervescence. Urease test was performed on Christensen's urea agar containing phenol red indicator and observing for color change from yellow to bright pink.

Fig. 6. Indole test results of all six isolates.

Fig. 7. Methyl red test results of all six isolates.

Fig. 8. Voges-Proskauer test results of all six isolates.

Fig. 9. Citrate utilization test results of all six isolates.

Fig. 10. Catalase test results of all six isolates showing gas bubble formation.

Fig. 11. Urease test results of all six isolates on Christensen's urea agar.

6. Secondary Screening by Nessler's Test:

Secondary screening was performed using Nessler's reagent as a quantitative colorimetric method for measuring ammonia production. All isolates were inoculated in L-glutamine broth and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. After incubation, culture filtrates were obtained by centrifugation

and treated with Nessler's reagent. Optical density was measured at 456nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer and compared against a standard ammonia curve to calculate the ammonia concentration per 5ml, which directly reflects L-glutaminase enzyme activity.

Fig. 12. Nessler's test showing yellow to brown color development indicating ammonia production by isolates.

Fig. 13. Standard ammonia curve with OD of isolates L1 to L6 plotted at 456nm for determination of ammonia concentration.

7. Enzyme Production and Crude Extract

Preparation:

The selected bacterial isolates were inoculated into sterilized production medium containing L-glutamine as nitrogen source with pH adjusted to 7.0. Inoculated flasks were

incubated at 37°C for 24 to 48 hours on a rotary shaker at 150 rpm. After incubation, the fermented broth was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. The clear supernatant obtained was collected as the crude enzyme extract and stored at 4°C for further analysis.

Fig. 14. Production medium inoculated with selected bacterial isolates for L-glutaminase enzyme production.

Fig. 15. Crude enzyme extract obtained after centrifugation of fermented culture broth.

Results:

1. Isolation and Primary Screening:

A total of six distinct bacterial isolates designated L1, L2, L3, L4, L5 and L6 were successfully obtained from garden and forest soil samples of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar on M9 minimal salt selective medium. All six isolates demonstrated visible growth, confirming their ability to utilize L-glutamine as the sole nitrogen source, which is indicative of L-glutaminase enzymatic activity. Primary screening using phenol red indicator confirmed extracellular L-glutaminase activity in all six isolates through development of distinct pink or magenta red halo zones around the colonies. The diameter of the halo zones varied among the isolates, indicating

differences in their relative enzyme production potential.

2. Morphological Characterization:

Gram staining results revealed that isolates L2, L3 and L6 were gram positive bacteria while isolates L1, L4 and L5 were gram negative bacteria. Negative staining confirmed that isolate L1 exhibited cocci shaped morphology while isolate L2 showed rod shaped and thread shaped cells. Isolates L3, L4, L5 and L6 all exhibited rod shaped morphology. The morphological diversity observed among the isolates indicates that L-glutaminase production is widely distributed across diverse bacterial taxonomic groups in soil, consistent with reports by Waykar et al. (2023) and Saleem and Ahmed (2020).

Table 1. Gram staining and negative staining results of all isolates.

Isolate	Gram Nature	Cell Morphology	Shape
L1	Gram Negative	Cocci	Spherical
L2	Gram Positive	Rod & Thread shaped	Bacillus
L3	Gram Positive	Rod shaped	Bacillus
L4	Gram Negative	Rod shaped	Bacillus
L5	Gram Negative	Rod shaped	Bacillus
L6	Gram Positive	Rod shaped	Bacillus

3. Biochemical Characterization:

IMViC test results showed that all six isolates were indole negative, suggesting absence of tryptophanase enzyme. Methyl red positivity was recorded in isolates L1, L2, L3 and L5, indicating their ability to produce stable mixed acid end products during glucose fermentation.

Voges-Proskauer test was negative for all isolates. Citrate utilization was positive only for isolate L3. All six isolates demonstrated strongly positive catalase and urease activity, confirming active aerobic metabolism and enzymatic versatility across all isolates.

Table 2. Biochemical characterization results of all six isolates.

Isolate	Indole	MR	VP	Citrate	Catalase	Urease	Gram Nature
L1	-	+	-	-	+	+	Negative
L2	-	+	-	-	+	+	Positive
L3	-	+	-	+	+	+	Positive
L4	-	-	-	-	+	+	Negative
L5	-	+	-	-	+	+	Negative
L6	-	-	-	-	+	+	Positive

(+) Positive, (-) Negative, MR: Methyl Red, VP: Voges-Proskauer

4. Secondary Screening by Nessler's Test:

Nessler's quantitative assay confirmed ammonia production in all six isolates. Isolate L6 demonstrated the highest ammonia concentration of 0.58 mg/L per 5ml with an optical density of 0.3870 at 450nm, clearly establishing it as the most potent L-glutaminase producer in the study. Isolate L3 followed with 0.55 mg/L and OD of 0.3579, while isolate L2 showed 0.50 mg/L with

OD of 0.3367. Isolates L4 and L5 showed intermediate enzyme activity with ammonia concentrations of 0.30 mg/L and 0.28 mg/L respectively. Isolate L1 demonstrated the lowest ammonia production of 0.25 mg/L. The significant variation in ammonia production among isolates is consistent with observations reported by Sinha and Nigam (2016) and Kaushal et al. (2023).

Table 3. Nessler's test results showing OD at 450nm and calculated ammonia concentration of all isolates.

Isolate	OD at 450nm	Ammonia Concentration (mg/L per 5ml)
L1	0.2351	0.25
L2	0.3367	0.50
L3	0.3579	0.55
L4	0.2537	0.30
L5	0.2621	0.28
L6	0.3870	0.58

5. Enzyme Production and Crude Extract:

The crude enzyme extract was successfully prepared from the fermented culture broth of all selected isolates by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. The clear supernatant obtained served as the crude enzyme extract containing extracellular L-glutaminase secreted by the bacterial isolates into the production medium during incubation. The crude extract is ready for further enzyme activity assay, protein estimation and purification studies.

Discussion:

The present study successfully demonstrated that soil from diverse local environments of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra is a rich source of L-glutaminase producing bacteria. The use of M9 minimal salt medium with L-glutamine as the sole nitrogen source proved to be a highly effective selective strategy, as only metabolically competent bacteria capable of hydrolyzing glutamine could grow, significantly enriching the target population from the complex soil microbiome. This selective approach is consistent with methodologies employed by Saleem and Ahmed (2020) and Al-Zahrani (2020) for isolation of glutaminase producing bacteria.

The development of pink or red halo zones around colonies in the phenol red primary screening is attributed to the release of ammonia during L-glutamine hydrolysis by L-glutaminase, causing an alkaline shift detected by the pH indicator. This simple colorimetric approach proved reliable for initial screening, consistent with findings of Al-Zahrani (2020) who validated phenol red-based plate assay as an efficient primary screening tool for glutaminase producing bacteria.

The morphological diversity observed among the six isolates, with both gram positive

and gram negative bacteria exhibiting L-glutaminase activity, confirms that this enzymatic capability is not restricted to any particular bacterial taxonomic group but is widely distributed in soil microbial communities. This observation is in agreement with Waykar et al. (2023) who reported diverse L-glutaminase producing bacteria from soil of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra, and with Saleem and Ahmed (2020) who reported significant taxonomic diversity among glutaminase producers.

The biochemical characterization results, particularly the universal positivity for catalase and urease among all isolates, suggest that the isolated bacteria are aerobic organisms with active nitrogen metabolism, which is consistent with the ecological role of L-glutaminase in nitrogen cycling. The methyl red positivity in four of the six isolates indicates mixed acid fermentation ability, suggesting metabolic flexibility that could be advantageous for enzyme production under varying fermentation conditions.

Among all isolates, L6 emerged as the most potent L-glutaminase producer with the highest ammonia concentration of 0.58 mg/L, followed by L3 and L2. The significant variation in enzyme production capacity among isolates from the same soil environment reflects the natural diversity of glutaminase-producing microorganisms and their varying enzyme titers, as similarly reported by Sinha and Nigam (2016) from *Bacillus* sp. and Kaushal et al. (2023) from *Pseudomonas* sp. The successful preparation of crude enzyme extract from all selected isolates provides a foundation for further purification and characterization studies aimed at developing novel microbial sources of L-glutaminase for biotechnological applications.

Conclusion:

The present study successfully isolated six L-glutaminase producing bacterial isolates from garden and forest soil of Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar using a systematic approach combining M9 selective medium, phenol red primary screening, morphological and biochemical characterization, and Nessler's quantitative secondary screening. Isolate L6 was identified as the most potent producer with the highest ammonia concentration of 0.58 mg/L, followed by L3 and L2. The crude enzyme extract was successfully prepared and is ready for further purification and characterization. These findings establish that local soil environments of Maharashtra are valuable sources of novel L-glutaminase producing bacteria with significant potential for biotechnological, therapeutic, food industry and agricultural applications. Future work should focus on molecular identification of the most potent isolate L6 using 16S rRNA gene sequencing, optimization of production parameters, purification of enzyme and evaluation of its antitumor, flavor-enhancing and biofertilizer potential.

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